

NUMERICAL PERMEABILITY PREDICTIONS OF WOVEN TEXTILES: EXAMINING THE CHARACTERISTICS OF MULTI- LAYER PREFORMS

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Keywords: Permeability, Textile Modelling, Liquid Composite Moulding

ABSTRACT

Liquid Composite Moulding (LCM) process simulations are increasingly used as process design tools to select optimal manufacturing parameters for fibre reinforced polymer (FRP) composite materials. Accurate permeability data of textile preforms is an essential input for these simulations. For maximum accuracy it is desirable to capture both the preform's permeability and its spatial variation.

An automated tool has been developed for generation of permeability predictions for multi-layered unit cells utilising textile modelling techniques. A reinforcing textile is initially scanned and its geometric parameters determined using image analysis techniques. Textile models of a single layer are then created and combined to replicate the stacking step during preform manufacturing. Compaction simulations are applied to these stacks, capturing changes in geometry as well as nesting. Voxel meshes representing the volume of resin around the compacted geometries are then exported. The voxel meshes are automatically cleaned, deleting any floating elements, and the boundary regions defined based on the unit cell size. By executing flow simulations on these meshes, the permeability characteristics of the preform are obtained.

The tool has been used to study the effect of preform structure on its permeability, including consideration of the number of layers, stacking sequence and ply shift. The analysis is verified by computing the full three-dimensional permeability, and comparing this to in-plane permeability data obtained experimentally.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fibre Reinforced Polymer Composite (FRPC) materials are used in a large number of industrial applications. FRPCs consist of two or more distinct materials (generally fibre reinforcement and polymer matrix), forming a material with more desirable properties. For applications where parts are mass produced and high levels of accuracy and repeatability are required, Liquid Composite Moulding (LCM) processes are the preferred manufacturing method [1]. In LCM processes, resin is injected into a mould containing the dry fibrous reinforcement and is left to cure before the final part can be removed from the mould.

The use of LCM simulations as process design tools is increasing in industry. These simulations are used to accurately predict fill time, flow front advancement and dry spot formation, ultimately enabling the production of complex high quality parts under the most efficient conditions [2]. In these simulations, the resin flow during the LCM manufacturing process is commonly modelled using Darcy's law [3]. The relation is given in Equation 1, where \mathbf{q} is the volume averaged Darcy velocity; μ , the fluid viscosity; P , the fluid pressure and \mathbf{K} , the permeability tensor. These simulations therefore require knowledge of the reinforcing material's permeability characteristics.

$$\mathbf{q} = -\frac{1}{\mu}\mathbf{K}\nabla P \quad (1)$$

Permeability, \mathbf{K} , is a measure of the ability of a reinforcement material to transmit fluids. It is an important material characteristic that determines the flow propagation of the resin during LCM manufacturing processes and is an indispensable input into LCM process simulations [4]. As the permeability behaviour of reinforcing textiles is a strong function of the textile's complex architecture [5] (which therefore makes the development of adequate analytical models extremely difficult), many researchers are relying on measurements obtained from experiment [6]. For this, many data points are required to capture the influence of manufacturing and handling induced variability, varying compaction levels, and the preform structure. This is time and labour intensive and the results can vary significantly as a result of a lack of a standardised testing method and errors involved in the handling process [7, 8].

This paper presents an automated tool that has been developed to predict the permeability of reinforcing textiles. The tool requires minimal input data and enables many different textiles and preform structures to be analysed efficiently. A number of results obtained using this tool are discussed, showing its full potential.

2 AUTOMATED PERMEABILITY PREDICTION TOOL

An automated tool has been developed, utilising textile modelling techniques [9] to generate permeability predictions for a range of textiles. Figure 1 outlines the steps involved in this prediction process. These steps are performed directly from the Matlab environment without any user intervention. When a step is completed using an external software package, the appropriate scripts are generated and executed from within Matlab. Such an automated tool enables the efficient analysis of a large number of unit cells of textile material. The results can then also be used to create a permeability map for a range of textile samples.

Figure 1: Automated tool steps.

Data about the textile's architecture is used to generate a range of unit cell geometries in TexGen [10]. This data can be obtained using automated image analysis techniques, as previously presented in [11]. In the textile models, the yarns are treated as solid volumes with the cross-section shape defined as the smallest ellipse that encompasses all the fibres within the yarn. To model multi-layer preform stacks, the single layer models are combined using the stacking sequence desired. An in-plane shift can also be applied, thereby controlling the level of nesting exhibited. Figure 2 illustrates a range of textile models that have been created using this method.

Figure 2: Textile models. (a) Single layer Plain Woven, (b) 4 layers stacked directly on top of each other, (c) 4 layers with maximum ply shift and (d) 4 layers with random ply shift.

Compaction simulations are applied to the textile models, reflecting the change of geometry due to the compaction step of the LCM process. The textile mesh is compacted between two rigid platens to achieve a target cavity thickness. Simple linear elastic material properties are assigned to the yarn bundles, capturing the predominant changes in geometry. Figure 3 shows examples of the 4 layer preform stack shown in Figure 2b compacted to different cavity thicknesses.

Figure 3: 4 layer textile model with maximum ply shift, compacted to a range of thicknesses. Resulting V_f of (a) 25%, (b) 34% and (c) 47%.

A novel algorithm to automatically generate a voxel mesh representing the volume of resin around the compacted mesh geometry is then applied. This is executed automatically and can account for cases where the compacted mesh contains small element intersections. The voxel mesh is then automatically cleaned to delete any floating elements (defined as voxels that are not connected to the main mesh). This enables the efficient execution of the flow simulations. The boundary regions are also defined, where the appropriate elements for each region are located by intersecting 2D planes at the corresponding locations with the mesh.

Flow simulations are carried out in Ansys CFX, with a pressure gradient imposed between the inlet and outlet boundaries. Non-slip wall conditions are imposed on the top and bottom surfaces of the unit cell as well as the boundaries between the fluid domain and the fibre yarns. Translational periodic boundaries are used for the two sides, to reflect the periodic structure of the textile [5]. These boundary conditions are illustrated on a single layer model in Figure 4. The values of the parameters used in these simulations (such as resin viscosity and pressure gradient) represent typical manufacturing cases. The resulting mass flow rate, \dot{m} , is used to compute the unit cell meso-scale permeability through the application of Darcy's law [6] as shown in Equation 2.

Figure 4: Flow simulation boundary conditions.

$$\mathbf{K} = \frac{\dot{m}\mu L}{A\rho\nabla P} \quad (2)$$

In order to compute the permeabilities of the unit cell in the different directions (e.g. weft and warp), the location of the boundaries are altered; however, the same mesh is used. This is shown in Figure 5 where the same mesh (generated from the compacted fibre mesh shown in Figure 3b) has been used to predict the full 3D permeability tensor. Velocity contour plots are presented, highlighting the flow channels in the preform structure.

Figure 5: Velocity contour plots of flow simulations carried out on the voxel mesh generated from the compacted fibre mesh shown in Figure 3b. Flow simulations in the (a) x, (b) y and (c) z directions.

Figure 6 presents the associated processing times to complete each step on the single layer unit cell model presented in Figure 2a. These times were achieved by executing the process on a Windows 7, 64 bit computer, with 8GB RAM and an Intel® Core™ i5-2500 CPU at 3.30GHz. As can be seen, the entire process takes 4.7 minutes, making the permeability prediction tool a much more time-efficient option than carrying out experiments. The longest components of the process are, as expected, the compaction and flow simulations.

Figure 6: Process times for a single layer model.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A range of results may be obtained using the permeability prediction tool. These are separated into single and multiple layer predictions.

3.1 Single Layer

The single layer model (shown in Figure 2a) was used to obtain in-plane permeability predictions at different compaction levels. This model was generated using average geometric parameters measured from a 800gsm plain woven glass reinforcement which was later used to carry out permeability experiments (using the methodology presented in [12]). The permeability predictions, as

shown in Figure 7, accurately capture the decreasing permeability trend with increasing fibre volume fraction (increasing level of compaction). The results obtained closely follow experimental results. Figure 8 presents the in-plane anisotropy ratio of the same textile (K_{xx}/K_{yy}). Again, the results obtained using the prediction tool are in close agreement with those observed from the experimental data.

Figure 7: K_{xx} with increasing V_f of the single layer model shown in Figure 2a.

Figure 8: In-plane anisotropy ratio (K_{xx} / K_{yy}) with increasing V_f of the single layer model shown in Figure 2a.

The prediction tool may also be used to generate complete permeability maps which reflect the inherent variability of the textile. A 250×250 mm sample of the 800gsm reinforcing textile was scanned and analysed to determine its geometry. 400 small unit cell models were then generated based on this geometry. The permeability of each was determined using the permeability prediction tool and, from the results, the contour plot shown in Figure 9 was created. This contour plot shows the significant variation in permeability in the y direction (K_{yy}) along with an outline of the reinforcement tows. It can be seen that the locations of higher permeability (shown in red) correspond to locations where the vertical gaps between the reinforcement tows are larger. This is as expected: larger gaps provide bigger flow channels for the fluid, thereby increasing the textile's permeability.

Figure 9: K_{yy} contour plot of a 250×250 mm sample with outline of textile tows.

3.2 Multiple Layers

Multi-layer permeability predictions were obtained for a range of preforms generated using the 800gsm Plain Woven Glass reinforcement. Figures 10, 11 and 12 illustrate the resulting permeabilities in the x, y and z directions respectively. In each of these, preforms of increasing number of layers were used, whereby the layers were stacked directly on top of each other (as shown in Figure 2b for a 4 layer preform). The preforms were then compacted to a specified thickness to achieve the target fibre volume fraction. The in-plane permeability values, K_{xx} and K_{yy} , appear to asymptote with increasing number of layers. This is as expected, as the contribution of the boundary effects on the preform lessen. In all three permeability plots, it can be seen that the permeability decreases with increasing fibre volume fraction as expected.

Figure 10: K_{xx} of preforms with increasing number of layers, stacked directly on top of each other, at different compaction levels.

Figure 11: K_{yy} of preforms with increasing number of layers, stacked directly on top of each other, at different compaction levels.

Figure 12: K_{zz} of preforms with increasing number of layers, stacked directly on top of each other, at different compaction levels.

Permeability prediction values were also obtained for preforms of varying number of layers with an applied shift between the layers. Figures 13-15 show the resulting predicted permeability in the x direction for the different fibre volume fractions examined. Here, preforms were created by (a) stacking the layers directly on top of each other, (b) by applying a maximum in-plane shift and (c) by applying a random in-plane shift (as shown in Figures 2b, 2c and 2d respectively).

Figures 13-15 show that the permeability is heavily influenced by the stacking method. The preforms that were created with maximum ply shift exhibit the lowest permeability as the alternating placements of the tows obstruct the flow channels. The results provided are also validated against permeability values obtained experimentally, using the same methodology as Liotier et. al [12]. No special attention was given to the layer shift achieved. The experimental results follow similar trends as observed in the predicted results and their values lie within the predicted spread. This provides further confidence in the application of textile modelling techniques in order to generate permeability predictions.

Figure 13: K_{xx} of preforms with increasing number of layers, stacked using different methods, compacted to a V_f of 25%.

Figure 14: K_{xx} of preforms with increasing number of layers, stacked using different methods, compacted to a V_f of 34%.

Figure 15: K_{xx} of preforms with increasing number of layers, stacked using different methods, compacted to a V_f of 47%.

3 CONCLUSIONS

An automated tool has been developed for the generation of permeability predictions of multi-layered textile models using textile modelling techniques. This tool is fully automated and requires minimal input data, providing an attractive alternative to carrying out costly experiments.

This tool has been used to predict the permeability characteristics of a range of different preform structures, capturing the effects of textile variability, number of layers, ply shift and applied compaction. Single layer permeability predictions were generated and presented, and the importance of capturing the structural variability within the reinforcing materials and its influence on the

permeability properties was illustrated. Multi-layer permeability prediction results captured the trends expected and also enabled the controlled study of the effect of ply shift, which would otherwise be difficult to achieve in experiments. The predicted values were validated through their close agreement with permeability results obtained experimentally.

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